

ON THIOALDEHYDES AND THIOKETONES. PART II.

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A general method for the synthesis of thiophens and endothiophens has been described. The autocondensation of certain α -keto-alcohols followed by an internal rearrangement in an atmosphere of H_2S furnishes endothiophens. A new synthesis of thiophens has also been achieved by an application of this reaction to unsaturated γ -diketones.

Certain α -keto-alcohols in the presence of alcoholic hydrogen chloride undergo autocondensation to γ -diketones which subsequently give rise to furan and endoxyfuran derivatives (Irvine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 950 ; 1907, 91, 1386).

The pronounced tendency of thioketones to form cyclic compounds suggested the possibility of the synthesis of thiophen and endothiophen derivatives from such reactions in the presence of hydrogen sulphide.

The reaction of benzoin with hydrogen sulphide in ethyl alcohol furnished three compounds (A) m.p. 195° , (B) m.p. 126° , (C) m.p. 97° . The compound (A) does not possess any thiol or thioketonic group. It gives the thiophen reaction with isatin. It forms a tetrabromo derivative by absorbing four atoms of bromine, which loses all its bromine on heating. This fact suggests that all the bromine atoms are attached to the sulphur atoms. Structure (I) has been suggested for (A) since on reduction it gives tetraphenylthiophen. An attempted synthesis of (A) from the interaction of hydrogen sulphide and dibenzoylstilbene failed. The reaction afforded a quantity of tetraphenylfuran evidently from the reduction of dibenzoylstilbene by hydrogen sulphide. This fact affords an additional proof of the endoxyfuran structure of dibenzoylstilbene as suggested by Japp (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 71, 1139). The presence of an ethoxy group has been confirmed in compound (B). Structure II ($R' = Et$) has been suggested for it since alcoholic hydrogen chloride could effect its conversion to (A). Evidence of a hydrogen atom in thiophen ring could also be gathered from its reaction with bromine. The substance absorbs five bromine atoms with evolution of hydrogen bromide and forms a compound for which structure (II) is evident.

The position of the ethoxy group has also been confirmed by the synthesis of (B) from III (R'=Et) and further application of this reaction has been established by isolating the corresponding compound (R'=Me). Thus it is clear that two processes take place simultaneously in this reaction :

(i) Alkylation of benzoin in the presence of alcoholic hydrogen chloride (Fischer, *Ber.*, 1893, 20, 2412).

(ii) Formation of a γ -thiodiketone which rearranges to endothiiothiophen derivative like the corresponding oxygenated compounds (Irvine, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 98, 952).

The existence of the thioiketone group has been confirmed in (C) and the formation of benzil-diphenylhydrazone from its interaction with phenylhydrazine suggested the structure (VII) for it. Synthesis of this compound could not be effected since sulphur could not be introduced into benzil. The formation of this compound through oxidation of (VI) seems likely in analogy with the behaviour of benzoin under similar conditions (Irvine, *loc. cit.*). The reaction of

benzoin in methyl alcohol with hydrogen sulphide furnished along with compound (A) another substance (D). The compound (D) does not contain any ketonic, thioketonic or thiol group. It gives the thiophen reaction and can be reduced to thionessal. Structure (V) has been suggested for it. It is also noteworthy that (V) could not be acetylated. A similar case has been reported by Irvine (*loc. cit.*). The synthesis of endothiophens by the interaction of the corresponding diketone with hydrogen sulphide failed. Enolisation of the diketone followed by the elimination of water took place before sulphur was introduced. Under similar conditions unsaturated γ -diketone *e.g.* dibenzoylstyrene (VIII) gave an endoxythiophen (IX) and the corresponding thiophen (X). The formation of thiophen obviously necessitates the reduction of (VIII) to (XI) by hydrogen sulphide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Tetraphenyl-2:5-endothiophen (I).—Hydrogen sulphide a passed (24 hours) through a solution of benzoin (15 g.) in alcoholic hydrochloric acid (500 c.c.) at 14°. The crystalline material was then collected and digested with ethyl alcohol. The insoluble portion was purified from a mixture of chloroform and ethyl alcohol and obtained as colourless silky needles, m.p. 195°. [Found: C, 79.7; H, 4.9; S, 14.8, M.W. (ebullioscopic in chloroform), 450. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{20}\text{S}_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 4.7, S, 15.2 per cent. M.W., 420].

The same compound was isolated by passing hydrogen sulphide through a solution of benzoin (5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (310 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride and containing aqueous hydrochloric acid (29 c.c., *d* 1.19).

The substance gave (colouration) with isatin and concentrated sulphuric acid. It could not be reduced by zinc and hydrochloric acid and was slowly attacked by permanganate.

Tetraphenyl-2 : 5-endothiothiophen Tetrabromide.—The above mentioned thiophen (3 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (20 c.c.) containing bromine (8 g.). The green precipitate which was immediately thrown down furnished deep green needles from chloroform, m.p. 139°. The parent compound was regenerated by boiling with ethyl alcohol or acetic acid. (Found : Br, 43.1. $C_{28}H_{20}Br_4S_2$ requires Br, 43.2 per cent).

Action of Hydriodic Acid on (I) and the Formation of Tetraphenylthiophen.—Tetraphenylendothiothiophen (6 g.) was mixed with aqueous hydriodic acid (30 c.c., *d* 1.7) in a Zeisel flask, and heated to 127° (4 hours). The mixture after cooling was diluted with excess of water and the precipitate was extracted with excess of hot alcohol. The yellow material which separated from hot alcohol furnished thionessal, m.p. 184°, as colourless needles from glacial acetic acid. (Found : C, 86.7; H, 5.1. $C_{28}H_{20}S$ requires C, 86.6; H, 5.1 per cent).

Tetraphenyl-3-ethoxy-4-hydro-2 : 5-endothiothiophen (II) and Dithiobenzil (VII).—Hydrogen sulphide was passed (2 hours) through a solution of benzoin (5 g.) in ethyl alcohol (100 c.c.) which had been previously saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at 0°.

The separated material was collected and boiled under reflux with a large excess of alcohol. The insoluble portion was tetraphenyl-2 : 5-endothiothiophen. The yellow material obtained from the alcoholic solution was purified from a mixture of acetone and alcohol and obtained as yellow cubes, m.p. 126°. [Found : C, 77.0; H, 5.6; S, 14.2; OEt, 8.9; M.W. (ebullioscopic in chloroform), 460. $C_{30}H_{26}OS_2$ (II) requires C, 77.2; H, 5.5; S, 13.7; OEt *, 9.6 per cent. M.W., 466]. The mother liquor of the reaction mixture was poured into ice and the semi-solid mass was collected and washed with hot aqueous alcohol. The residue furnished greenish yellow cubes from absolute alcohol, m.p. 97°. [Found : C, 69.2; H, 4.4; S, 26.0. $C_{14}H_{10}S_2$ (VII) requires C, 69.4; H, 4.1; S, 26.4 per cent].

The Formation of Tetraphenyl-2:5-endothiothiophen from Tetraphenyl-3-ethoxy-4-hydro-2:5-endothiothiophen.—Tetraphenyl-3-ethoxy-4-hydro-2:5-endothiothiophen (5 g.) was dissolved in alcoholic hydrochloric acid (100 c.c.),

* The estimation of ethoxyl in this compound was carried out by Zeisel's method with some modification. The exit gases from the flask were passed through water kept at 75°. The black precipitate in the flask containing silver nitrate, evidently a mixture of silver sulphide and iodide, was digested with concentrated nitric acid, filtered and washed with water. The silver iodide remaining was dried and weighed.

d 1.19) and the mixture was boiled for 6 hours. The solid separating on cooling was digested with absolute alcohol. The needles, m.p. 195°, isolated from chloroform were identical with tetraphenyl-2:5-endothiothiophen. The same compound was also isolated on treating the ethoxy thiophen (II) with aqueous hydriodic acid (d 1.7) at 90°.

Tetraphenyl-3-ethoxy-4-bromo-2:5-endothiothiophen Tetrabromide (IV).—Tetraphenyl-3-ethoxy-2:5-endothiothiophen (3 g.) was dissolved in chloroform (15 c.c.) to which bromine (6 g.) was subsequently added. The mixture was then kept at 15° (2 hours). The precipitate obtained by adding of an excess of chloroform melted at 178°. [Found: C, 41.3; H, 2.6; Br, 47.0. $C_{30}H_{23}OBr_3S_2$ requires C, 41.6; H, 2.8; Br, 46.3 per cent].

Action of Hydrogen Sulphide on Ethoxydeoxybenzoin (III, R'=Et) and the Formation of (I), (II) and (VII).—Hydrogen sulphide was passed through a solution (12 hours) of ethoxydeoxybenzoin (10 g.) in ethyl alcohol (100 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride at 0°. The material which separated was boiled with ethyl alcohol in which (I) was insoluble. From the alcoholic solution (II) was isolated. This compound was also obtained by passing hydrogen sulphide through a solution of ethoxydeoxybenzoin (5 g.) in methyl alcohol (30 c.c.) saturated with dry hydrogen chloride. This fact proves that the solvent does not take part in this reaction. The mother liquor after isolation of (I) and (II) was rendered turbid with water. The precipitate furnished (VII) from alcohol.

3-Methoxy-4-hydroxytetraphenyl-2:5-endothiothiophen (II, R = Me).—Methoxydeoxybenzoin (R=Me, 6 g.) was dissolved in methyl alcohol (100 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride at 0°, and hydrogen sulphide was passed (12 hours). The precipitate was collected and extracted with boiling alcohol (200 c.c.). The residue was identified as tetraphenyl-2:5-endothiothiophen, m.p. 195°. The material obtained from the alcoholic extract furnished yellow needles from a mixture of acetone and alcohol. (Found: C, 77.0; H, 5.3; S, 13.7. $C_{28}H_{24}OS_2$ requires C, 77.0; H, 5.3; S, 14.1 per cent).

3-Hydroxy-4-hydroxytetraphenyl-2:5-endoxythiophen (V).—Benzoin (20 g.) was dissolved in methyl alcohol (500 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride. Hydrogen sulphide was passed (24 hours) at 15°. The mixture was poured into ice and the pasty mass was digested with acetone. The insoluble portion was tetraphenyl-2:5-endothiothiophen. The acetone solution furnished greenish yellow cubes, m.p. 165°, on addition of alcohol. (Found: C, 79.4; H, 5.4; S, 7.7. $C_{28}H_{22}OS_2$ requires C, 79.6; H, 5.2; S, 7.6 per cent).

The endoxythiophen (4 g.) was kept at 127° (4 hours) with aqueous hydriodic acid (30 c.c., *d* 1.7). Tetraphenylthiophen was isolated as before.

Action of Hydrogen Sulphide on Dibenzoylstilbene.—Hydrogen sulphide was passed (4 hours) through a solution of dibenzoylstilbene (3 g.) dissolved in alcohol (250 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride. The precipitate furnished tetraphenylfuran, m.p. 174°, as colourless plates from acetic acid. (Found : C, 90.3 ; H, 5.2. $C_{24}H_{20}O$ requires C, 90.3 ; H, 5.3 per cent).

The Formation of 2:4:5-Phenylthiophen (X) and its Endoxy-derivative (IX).—Hydrogen sulphide was passed (6 hours) through a solution of dibenzoylstyrene (3 g.) in alcohol (50 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride at 15°. The material which separated on standing overnight was boiled with excess of alcohol. The insoluble portion gave yellow plates (X) from acetic acid, m.p. 198°. (Found : C, 84.8 ; H, 5.3 ; S, 10.0. $C_{22}H_{16}S$ requires C, 84.6 ; H, 5.1 ; S, 10.2 per cent), and (IX) was isolated as yellow cubes from the alcoholic solution, m.p. 157°. (Found : C, 80.1 ; H, 4.8 ; S, 9.5. $C_{22}H_{16}OS$ requires C, 80.4 ; H, 4.8 ; S, 9.7 per cent).

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